

Marketing of Milk and Milk Products through Dairy Co-Operatives in Karnataka

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Milk Product Sector-KMF

Karnataka Milk federation which is most popular as KMF. The Karnataka Co- operative milk producers federation Ltd., a cooperative apex body in Karnataka, has been implementing Dairy Development activities in the entire state since 3 decades in a phased manner through the 13 district milk union, ushering prosperity in the lives of rural Milk Producers.

- The first ever World Bank funded Dairy Development integrated project was launched in 1975 on co-operative principles covering 8 southern districts initially and KDDC was setup for implementation.
- KMF came into existence in 1984 and Dairy Development activities were extended to cover the entire state under Operation Flood-11.
- OF-11 ended in 1987 and the process of Dairy Development continued through 13 District Milk Unions under OF- 111 from 1987 to 1996.
- The post operation Flood and Perspective Plan works are carried out from 1996 in coordination with NDDB.

Objectives

- To build primary Dairy Co-operative Societies in co-operative sector to manage the dairy activities.
- Providing assured and remunerative market for the milk produced by the farmer members.
- Providing quality milk & milk products to urban consumers.
- To ensure provision of milk production inputs, processing facilities and dissemination of knowhow.
- To facilitate rural development by providing opportunities for self employment at village level, preventing migration to urban areas, introducing cash economy and opportunity for steady income.

Affiliated Milk Unions

The Federation in its fold has 13 District Milk Unions spread-over the entire State of Karnataka-Bangalore, Mysore, Tumkur, Hassan, Mandya, kolar, Dharwar, Belgaum, Bijapur, Bellary, Gulbarga, D. Kannada and Shimoga milk unions.²⁴

Units of KMF

The following KMF Units are in operation to cater to the needs of centralized technical Input facilities.²⁵

1. Mother Dairy, Yelahanka, Bangalore (including Ice Cream plant, powder plant)
2. Nandini Milk Products, KMF Complex, Bangalore.
3. Cattle Feed Plant, Rajankunte.
4. Cattle Feed Plant, Gubbi.
5. Cattle Feed Plant, Dharwad.
6. Cattle Feed Plant, Hassan.
7. Nandini Sperm Station, Hessarghatta.
8. Pouch Film Factory, Munnekolala.
9. Central Training Institute, Bangalore & regional training centers at Dharwad & Mysore.

Physical Achievements

As at the end of December 2017, 11500 Dairy Co-operative Societies (DCS) have been organized covering 20193 villages in 13 milk Unions area. 9793 DCS are functioning with 97% of them in profit.

19.92 lakhs farmers are members in these DCS out of which of 6.29 lakhs are women members, 7.43 lakhs are small Farmers, 5.70 lakhs are Marginal Farmers, 3.56 lakhs are landless labourers and 3.23 lakhs are others. In total 2.09 and 1.14 lakhs of them belong to SC and STs.

Milk Procurement

Dairy Co-operative societies, in villages, are procuring milk from the member producers twice in a day. The average daily procurement is 42.85 lakhs kg during 2009-10 up to December 2010. The peak procurement was 45.22 lakh kgs. The surplus milk was converted in to milk products.

Karnataka Milk Federation is in second position, as far as milk procurement is concerned at the National. Twenty dairies with a total processing capacity of 26.65 lakhs ltr. Per day. 44 milk chilling centers with chilling capacity 15.00 lakhs ltrs. Per day and 4milk powder plants with drying capacity of 62 MT per day, are functioning.

During the year 2009-10 an average of 22.49 lakhs ltrs per day is sold as fluid milk out of which, an avg. of 13.01 lakh. Ltrs is sold in Bangalore city. To meet the demand of consumers, milk products like, Goodlife, UHT milk in different variants, Curds, Butter, Ghee, SMP, flavoured Milk (in 8 Flavors), Mysore pak, Nandini premium burfi, peda, Khova, Paneer, Chashew Burfi, Rasgulla, Badam Powder, Jamoon Mix, Jammon Container, Nandini Bite and Yoghurt are produced and sold. In addition to these, other products like sweet curds, “ Kudike Mosaru” (Curds in Pots), Butter Milk, Ice Cream and Kunda are also being produced and sold. In addition to these products flavoured milk and butter milk, in attractive tetra pack, has been released to the market.

Performance Highlights

- State entirely covered by Dairy Development.²⁸
- Elected board, in position, in all District Milk Unions & Federation.

- Low price spread between procurement and sale prices resulted in payment of higher price to the milk producers.
- 97% of the Milk producers Co- Operative Societies are earning profit.
- At present an average payment of Rs. 407 lakhs/day is made to milk producers.
- Implementation of ‘ Yashaswini Health Insurance Scheme’ to benefit farmer families of Dairy Co-Operatives.
- The four cattle Feed Plants Owned by KMF have been awarded with the ISO 9001:2000 certificate for best maintained quality standards by Indian Register Quality systems accredited by RVA.
- Nandini Sperm station has been awarded with ISO certificate & has been merited by Ministry of Agriculture, GOI as 2nd best A grade semen station in the country during 2005-06.
- KMF has exported SKIM Milk powder to Nepal, Bangladesh, Oman, Madagaskar, Burma, Singapore, Thailand & Phillipines.
- Mother Dairy, Bangalore has obtained clearance from Export Inspection Agency, Ministry of Commerce, and Govt. of India for export of Skim Milk Powder.
- Establishment of 6 lakh litres/day state of art, fully automated Mega Dairy in Bangalore expandable to 10 lakh litres/day.
- Kolar, Mysore, Dakshina Kannada & Tumkur Unions have obtained ISO 9001-2000. HACCP & CM certificates.
- B’ lore Milk Union has obtained ISO 2002005, which is the first dairy in south India to get the Certification. Mother Dairy has also obtained this certificate recently.
- About 6500 MTs of Nandini Ghee has been supplied during 2001-2010 to Thirumala Thirupathi Devasthanam.
- Dividend and bonus of Rs. 10.49 crores for the period 2001-2009 has been distributed by KMF out of profits made to share holders and unions.
- Area-specific Mineral Mixture production started in Gubbi Cattle Feed Plant with the technical guidance of NIANP Bangalore.
- Karnataka Milk Federation is successfully implementing Central Government Schemes, such as Clean Milk Production Programme, Special Package for suicide Prone Districts, Fodder Development etc., and State Government Schemes such as ‘Amruta Yojane’.
- Opening of ‘Nandini Dairy Farmers Welfare Trust’ Hostel for Farmers Children at the cost of Rs.12.96 Crore for higher education of 600 Boys and 400 Girls.

The Developmental Programmes

- A New 300MTs balanced Cattle feed Plant, to meet burgeoning demand for balanced cattle feed in the state, is being constructed at Hassan with an outlay of 39 Crores.29
- Strengthening/Expansion of Mother Dairy, Bangalore adopting modern technology from 4 LLPD to 7LLPD of milk handling facilities at an outlay of Rs. 35 crores.
- A new state of the art product plant is being commissioned at Channarayapatna in Hassan district at a cost of Rs.72 crore to handle surplus milk of Mysore, Tumkur, Hassan and Mandya Milk Unions.
- To implement an Integrated Development Plan at Northern Karnataka in the areas of Dairying and Horticulture on partnership basis with one of the NDDDB designated/subsidiary company or with m/s. Tetra Pak.
- Establishing a modern Cattle Feed Plant of 500 MTs capacity near Bangalore.
- To provide support in establishing necessary chilling infrastructure in the form of Bulk Milk Coolers.

- Expansion of Bangalore Mega Dairy processing capacity and establishing value added product plant.
- Expansion of Kolar, Mysore, Tumkur, Mandya, Hassan and Shimoga Dairy processing capacities and strengthening of chilling facilities.
- Modernisation of Mandya Powder Plant strengthening of chilling facilities.
- Establishing new dairy at Davangere district of Shimoga Milk Union and Strengthening at Chilling facilities.
- Establishment of modernized Nandini Milk Products Plant at an estimated cost of Rs. 10.00 crores.

Table 5.6 The Progress Achieved of Milk Unions During (as on 31-12-2017)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Unit	Progress
1	Dcs functioning	No.	9793
2	Women Dcs functioning	No.	1940
3	Bulk milk coolers	No.	383
4	Automatic milk collection centres	No.	1729
5	Members enrolled	(in lakh No.s)	
	a. Small Farmers	“	7.43
	b. Marginal Farmers	“	5.70
	c. Landless Labourers	“	3.56
	d. Others	“	3.23
	e. Total	“	19.92
	i. S.C	“	2.09
	ii. S.T	“	1.14
	iii. Women	“	6.29
6	Cattle feed sold (MTs)	“	210300
7	Avg. Procurement/day (Rs. In Crores)	“	32.85
8	Amount paid to producers/ day (Rs. In Crores)	“	4.07
9	a. Avg. Retail Sales/day (LLPD)	“	22.49
	b. Bangalore City Sales/day (LLPD)	“	22.00
10	Turnover (KMF and Unions) Rs. In crores	“	2750

Source: Karnataka Milk Federation, Bangalore

Milk and Milk Products Order

During the year 1992, Government of India had promulgated an act called MMPO 1992, for enforcement throughout the Country, which provides power to exercise control over milk products. Any firm or individual who procures, processes stores or markets in excess of 10,000 litres of milk per day or 500 metric tones of milk products per annum, need to obtain a registration certificate compulsorily either from State Registering Authority or Central Registering Authority.

To start with, the State Registering Authority issued the licenses to dairies, which handle milk upto 75,000 litres day or 500 metric tones of milk products per annum. In the subsequent amendments the powers of the State Registering authority have been enhanced initially from 75,000 litres of milk per day to 1,00 lakh litres and afterwards to 2.00 lakh litres of Milk per day. The movement

of milk has been totally decentralized in the country from 1-4-2002. So far, 16 milk- processing dairies have been registered by the Central Registering Authority and 23 milk-processing dairies.

Marketing of Milk

A market is defined as a public space for the purpose of buying and selling. Permanent markets are those where business transactions are carried out from day to day. While the temporary ones may be weekly, biweekly, casual or occasional, most held in connection with one or other annual fairs or shandy day. Marketing involves the permanence of services necessary to move goods into possession and ownership of final consumers. The services usually required in the marketing of agricultural products are a) processing b) grading c) packing d) storing e) financing f) transporting g) selling and h) risk bearing.

Some of the services are performed more than once in the marketing process. To simplify marketing includes movement of goods from producer to consumer. The market wherever located is a place where selling price is determined. Price again depends on several major relationships.

1. Supply and demand for products.
2. Accuracy and availability of market news.
3. Adequacy of information to dealer and buyer with respect to quality of the product offered.
4. Volume of stock needed for efficient operation.
5. Competition among buyers.

There are three principle parties involved in the economic activities of marketing the producers, the middleman and consumers. The producer will aim at a profit-something which is in addition to the cost involved in production. The consumer aims at his satisfaction and a reasonable price.

Livestock industry is a subsidiary village industry having the farm family as the unit of production. The farmer and his family contribute all that is required for running of this like capital, labour, etc. In return they expect a margin of return which would be fair and comparable to that obtained by workers in any other field. But in India, unfortunately it is not so always. Firstly, in the marketing aspect itself they suffer various handicaps, production is only a subsidiary, people engaged entirely in livestock production are very few. There are small individual units and the producers are very few. There are small individual units and the producers are ignorant of the demand and the supply price at different levels. It is here that the middle men play an important role and claim a very large share of the deal. The part played by the middleman has become a matter of controversy. While some give prominence to the group for their invaluable work, some wish for their elimination since they want direct dealing by the producer with the consumer. But the production to the consumption, there is a long way to go over which it would be difficult for the farmer to supervise and waste his time, experience and consequent fall in production. The middle man does a number of services like collection, storing and distribution of products from the producing units to the consuming markets. He knows the demand and makes the proper supply of the products. Hence its place becomes inevitable.

But one should not forget that the middleman is nothing but a middle man. He bears no risk and thrives even during adverse conditions of the producing units. He takes a good share of percentage to the score of 30% to 40% of the price paid by consumer. Co-operative societies when organized may perhaps see the elimination of this set of people as has been done in the case of milk and eggs in the State of Karnataka. But to this day the middleman thrives, which only shows that there are yet to be more co-operative societies for various other livestock products alone. There is need for co-operative societies for producers and co-operative associations to eliminate the problems of small breeders. The State of Karnataka no doubt provided guidance of technical and financial assistance to some extent, but the number of stock-breeders is so large that it is not possible to extend assistance to all. The only way to rectify this is by establishing dairy co-operative societies for market activities in large numbers in the State.

Liquid Milk Market

The liquid milk market has emerged as the most dynamic segment of the dairy industry growing at CAGR of 10 per cent. The urban dairy market, dominated by liquid milk, has many exciting opportunities for the entrepreneur. It cannot be regarded as homogeneous, but layered, with each layer offering its own rewards. In the organized sector, the share of 3% fat toned milk exceeded 50%, 4.5% standardized milk stood at 33% and 6% fat full-cream milk was 9%.

The co-operative and public sector dairies meet 40 per cent of the liquid milk demand in Class-I cities. The balance is shared by the private organized and traditional non-organized sectors. Presently, only some 1,000 out of 5,000 cities and towns in India are served by its milk distribution network, dispensing hygienically packed wholesome, quality pasteurized milk rising awareness about hygienic standards and adulteration of loose milk has led consumers in urban areas to switch to pasteurized packaged milk.

The organized sector is beginning to tap the demand for low-fat milk in 200ml sachets and is selling milk in small towns with an average demand of 10,000 liters per day. The traditional dudh wala scores over the organized sector by selling small quantities (100ml to 250ml) of milk, ensuring home delivery and giving milk on credit for one month. It wins the consumers confidence with the concepts with him, some co-operatives have initiated home delivery free of cost.

Marketing of Milk and Milk Products

Milk and milk products are sold under 'Nandini' brand name, which has become household name in Karnataka. Nandini brand has become most trusted channel for rural producer prosperity and has also become most favorite dairy brand of consumers in the State. Nandini has also become lifeline for the milk producers. Co-operative Milk Unions and the Federation in Karnataka.

'NANDINI' brand has 40 numbers of product ranges in its family and popular with different milk variants. Surpluses and deficiencies of liquid milk amongst the member milk unions and sale of bulk milk to the sister Units. Federations, outside agencies, arranging roadmilk tankers, co-ordinating with powder plants within and outside the state for timely drying of surplus milk is the responsibility of the Federation. The bulk sale of milk products outside the state is also the responsibility of the Federation.

The milk which was being sold in bottles with limited availability in the by gone era, has transformed long way in adopting sachet packets in 1980, a safer & sterilized-60 days shelf life-Tetra Fino pack milk, with wider availability of milk & milk products to consumers in different sales outlets spread across the State viz, through, agents, parlours, Nandini milk shoppes, day counters and also on a display cum mobile van popularly know as 'Nandini shop on Wheels'.

In respect of disposal of products in retails packs and to make products with wide reach to consumers, depot concept of centralized marketing system on the lines of GCMMF (Gujarat co-operative milk marketing federation), has been introduced from Dec.1994. The federation distributes the products of milk unions by establishing distribution network and sales depots at Bangalore, Hubli, Mangalore Tirupati, Kannur & Ernakulam comprising of 202 wholesale dealers spread across Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Goa & Tamilnadu States of India and catering around 20000 retail outlets. The dealer network is being expanded to increase sales volume in other States also.

In addition to the products sold in the retail packs, the products are sold in bulk to the neighbouring Federations, MNC's, private traders, Institutions like TTD (Tirumala Tirupati Devasthanam) and Exports are the other activities of Marketing Division.

The innovations also include

- Introduction of new products
- Its price fixation & packing size

- New packaging designs
- Advertisement plans.

Campaigns are undertaken by Marketing division. Providing POP, Advt., materials, Organization of Workshops/Seminar to improve the quality of the products is another important function of marketing division. Public relation activity is also taken care by the division. In conformity with uniform symbol 'Mnemonic' which majority of the Milk Unions have adopted for liquid milk marketing, the NDDB has provided marketing assistance by way of advertisement during the initial years of introduction.

The Many Variants of Nandini

Milk is marketed under 'Nandini' brand in different types as

- Toned Milk
- Homogenized Toned Milk
- Homogenized Cow Milk
- Standardized Milk
- Full Cream Milk
- Shubham Milk
- Lite Skimmed Milk

The major products include Nandini Curds, Nandini Ghee, Butter, Skim Milk Powder, Badam Powder, Paneer, Peda, Mysore Pak, Burfi, Jamoons, Khova, Flavoured Milk and Ice Cream. The brand Nandini has become sunonym for milk and milk products. The easy availability of high quality Nandini Milk products in nook and corner of the State has made Nandini to occupy this pride place in the minds of the customer. Mysore pak has attained unassailable quality standards. It is popular even in overseas.

Nandini Ghee is know for quality and aroma and is one of the largest selling Ghee brand in South India. The Ghee quality conforms to special AGMARK quality standards. It is made available not only in 50 ml, 100ml, 200ml, 500ml & 1 ltr, pouches but also in 500 ml, 1 ltr, 5 ltr pearlpet jars and in 15 kg tins. Delicious Nandini ghee has become an indispensable ingredient sought for preparing prasadam of Lord Venkateshwars.

KMF, by adopting Ultra High Temperature (UHT) treatment technology has introduced milk with a shelf life of 60 days without refrigeration, under the brand name 'Nandini Good life' packed at Kolar Milk Union. In order to meet the requirement and convenience of different segment of the consumers, currently UHT milk is being marketed in following variants viz.

- Nandini Goodlife with 3.5% Fat and 8.5% SNF 200ml, 1ltr Brik and 500ml Fino pack
- Nandini Smart with 1.5% Fat and 9% SNF 500 MI Fino pack
- Nandini Goodlife Slim with 0.5% Fat and 9%SNF 1 ltr Brik and 500 ml Fino pack In addition, New Generation Drinks in new Tetra pack variants of Flavoured Milk/Butter are introduced.

Mysore Milk Fed's Expansion

The Mysore and Chamarajanagar Milk Federation had drawn up a blue print to upgrade itself into a mega dairy by 2020. Besides fully computerizing for effective management, the Federation has proposed to step up its milk production and launch a variety of new products into the market. By 2015, it plans to increase milk collection to 500,000 kg from the present 180,000kg milk daily, close to three times growth. It is currently selling 180,000 kg milk and 30,000 kg curds, apart from a variety of milk-based products. It has expanded its market by supplying 'Nandini' ghee from the Mysore Dairy to Tirupati for preparation of 'laddus', to Kottakal Arya Vaidyashala in Kerala for manufacture of ayurvedic medicines. In view of increasing demand in Kerala and Tamil Nadu for milk and its products, it has drawn up a marketing strategy to set up a cold storage at H D Kote, bordering the two States.

Price of Milk

There seems to reliable published data are available regarding the price of milk in the State. In real sense, there has hardly been any significant rise in the price of milk over the last decades. While the price of manufactured milk products has shown tremendous increase. It has been observed that at the time of arrival of new product in the market there is cartel formation by the traders and the procurement process are deliberately kept very low. The socio-economic conditions of the cattle rearers and poor storing capacity at their places which have forces them to sell their milk at the price dictated by the petty merchants. Adding this, imperfect knowledge of producer about milk price structure, the monopolistic practices at the time of auction of milk by the agent and non-interference of Government staff in the free market transactions have been tremendously affect the price structure of milk. The liberal import policy of Government on milk products with provisions for stock and sale have further aggravated the situation.

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